

Research

Assessment of Prevalence of Dental Caries and Its Associated Risk Factors in Diabetic Patients in Madhesh Province, Nepal

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Abstract: Objective: To explore the dental caries status and their predisposing factors for individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM), with impaired glucose regulation (IGR) and with normal glucose tolerance (NGT) respectively.

Methods: In this study 145 patients with DM, 140 individuals with IGR and 149 individuals with NGT (served as control group) were randomly selected. Oral examination was carried out and fasting plasma glucose (FPG) levels, plasma glucose level of 2 hours post glucose-load (PG2h), resting salivary flow rates, salivary pH value were tested in Janaki Medical College, Teaching Hospital, Janakpur, Madhesh Province, Nepal.

Results: For DM, IGR and control group, the caries rate was 72.4%, 69.2%, 63.8% respectively with no significant difference among them. DMFT (caries mean) in DM group was significantly higher than that in IGR and control group ($P < 0.05$). The means of resting salivary flow rate and salivary pH value in DM and IGR group were lower than in the control group; while the mean of FPG value in DM and IGR group were higher than in the control group ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Patients with DM have more possibilities of dental caries than individuals with IGR or healthy control. Controlling diabetes mellitus may help to reduce the number of dental caries.

Keywords: diabetes mellitus; dental caries; Caries prevalence

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a common chronic disease that has emerged as a major health-care problem. In 2019, the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) estimated that 463 million adults worldwide had diabetes[1]. The statistics showed that these individuals were in the age range of 20 to 79, have diabetes, and 79.4% were from low- and middle-income countries. Additionally, IDF estimates that the global prevalence of diabetes will be 578.4 million by 2030, with this rising to 700 million by 2045 among adults aged between 20 to 79 years[2]. In the region of Southeast Asia, the

prevalence of diabetes was 8.8% in 2019, and this is projected to increase to 9.7% by 2030. T2DM still remains a major cause of worldwide morbidity and mortality, which leads to complications such as neuropathy, nephropathy, stroke, and coronary artery disease[3]. In 2017, over 10,000 individuals died due to T2DM or diabetes-related complications in Nepal, which is the 11th most common cause of disability in terms of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) (1226 DALYs per 10,000 population)[4]. In 2020, the prevalence of T2DM in Nepal was 8.5% (95% CI 6.9–10.4%), which was higher than that of 8.4% (95% CI 6.2–10.5%) in 2014. Similarly, in 2020 the prevalence of pre-diabetes was 9.2% (95% CI 6.6 – 12.6%) compared to 2014, which was 10.3% (95% CI 6.1–14.4%)[5].

A very high and appalling prevalence of dental caries is found in diabetic patients compared to nondiabetics. It has been reported in the literature from previous studies that risk of dental caries is more prevalent in patients with type-II DM compared to nondiabetics. DM is responsible for causing ascendancy in the proportion and activity of saliva that impacts the oral health. Dental caries is caused by demineralization that is triggered by the accumulation of microbial plaque flora, decrease in the flow rate of saliva causing reduction in the cleansing, and buffer activity and diminished levels of calcium that is essential for the repair of decayed tooth.[6]

Saliva is essential for maintaining the oral equilibrium and the effects of saliva and its constituents on the oral microorganisms that influence the development of dental caries. Salivary components (immunoglobulins, salivary protein, salivary calcium, and inorganic phosphorous and alkaline phosphatase levels), its flow rate, viscosity, buffering capacity, pH, etc., plays a major role in initiation and progression of dental caries[7]. The average value of whole saliva as per various studies conducted on unstimulated saliva is found to be 0.3 mL/min. If the values are found to be less than 0.1 mL/min, it is a case of hyposalivation.[5] The normal value of salivary pH is 5.6–7.9, whereas the normal levels of salivary calcium is found to be 4–6 mg/mL[8].

Research Methodology

The subjects in our analysis comprises of 145 patients with type-II DM, 140 individuals with IGR and 149 individuals with NGT (served as control group) within the age group of 30–65 years. Diabetic status was assessed by estimating random blood glucose levels. Dental findings were recorded using modified World Health Organization (WHO) Oral health survey-basic method 2013. Salivary samples from all the subjects were collected and sent to the laboratory for interpretation of pH, flow rate. The analysis of salivary components decayed tooth was carried using analysis of variance (ANOVA). All the parameters were subjected to statistical analysis using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0. The age, caries average, saliva volume, saliva pH value and fasting blood Sugar was subjected to one-way analysis of variance and LSD test between multiple groups. The chi-square test was conducted on gender, caries incidence rate, and caries-deficient composition ratio. The significance value is $P < 0.05$.

This study was approved by the Ethical Committee of NHRC, Nepal. The data were collected from 2023-09-27 to 2023-12-26 in Janaki Medical College, Teaching Hospital, Janakpurdham, Madhesh Province, Nepal. The three groups of subjects were investigated using a unified epidemiological questionnaire. The survey content included: the general situation of the respondents, diabetes history, smoking history, denture wearing, systemic disease status, oral examination, fasting plasma glucose (FPG), plasma glucose level of 2 hours post glucose-load (PG2h), static saliva flow, and saliva pH. Finally, a total of 434 people were included in the statistical analysis. Examined the condition of the subjects' entire mouth, and the assistant recorded the number of decayed, missing and filled teeth (DMFT). The examination standard was based on the oral health survey method recommended by WHO and the second national oral epidemiological survey method [1, 2]. The third molars were not included. The Kappa value of the repeated examination standard consistency test was greater than 0.8.

Inclusion criteria: According to the 2019 WHO DM diagnosis and classification criteria, the subjects were divided into the following three groups [3]: DM group: $FPG \geq 7.0$ mmol/L, $PG2h \geq 11.1$ mmol/L; symptoms of polydipsia, polyphagia, polyuria, and weight loss. IGR group: included three types: ① impaired fasting glucose (IFG), $FPG \geq$

6.1mmol/L and <7.0mmol/L; ② impaired glucose tolerance (IGT), FPG <6.1mmol/L, PG2h ≥ 7.8mmol/L and <11.1mmol/L); ③ both IFG and IGT. Control group: FPG <6.1mmol/L, PG2h <7.8mmol/L.

Exclusion criteria: History of head, neck and face radiotherapy, various types of hepatitis infection, AIDS, lymphoma, sarcoidosis, graft-versus-host disease, and the use of anti-acetylcholine drugs (such as atropine, scopolamine, propantheline bromide, belladonna, etc.) excluded.

The statistical method uses SPSS 11.5. The age, caries average, saliva volume, saliva pH value and fasting blood Sugar was subjected to one-way analysis of variance and LSD test between multiple groups. The chi-square test was conducted on gender, caries incidence rate, and caries-deficient composition ratio. The significance value is $P < 0.05$.

Results

Among 434 patients, 75% of them were uneducated patients, and their living environment was basically the same. Those who met the inclusion criteria and gave informed consent were divided into the DM group, IGR group, and control group. After statistical analysis, there was no significant difference in age and gender between the groups ($P > 0.05$), indicating that the age and gender were well matched between the groups. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 – Comparison of gender and age among cases in DM group, IGR group and control group(NGT).

Group	Number of cases	Male	Female	Age (mean ± standard deviation)
DM	145	66	79	66.59±10.21
IGR	140	64	76	64.59±11.39
NGT	149	72	77	65.52±10.83
Total	434	202*	232*	65.58±10.82**

* Gender of each group of subjects $X^2 = 0.290, p = 0.865 > 0.05$

** Homogeneity of variance of age of each group of subjects $P = 0.354, F = 1.222, P = 0.296 > 0.05$

Comparison of caries incidence of DM group, IGR group and control group were 72.4%, 69.2% and 63.8%, respectively. There was no significant difference among the three groups ($P > 0.05$); the average caries number of DM group, IGR group and control group was 3.79, 2.44 and 2.81 teeth, respectively. The caries number of the three groups was analyzed by variance analysis and LSD test. The differences between DM group and IGR group and control group were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$); there was no significant difference between IGR group and control group ($P > 0.05$), indicating that DM group had more serious caries than IGR group and control group, see Table 2.

Table 2 – caries rate and caries ratio of DM group, IGR group and control group(NGT) were compared.

Group	Number of cases	Dental caries cases	Caries rate%	Number of cases without dental caries	No dental caries rate%	Caries mean ± SD
DM	145	105	72.4	39	27.9	3.79 ± 5.333 △▲
IGR	140	97	69.2	48	33.1	2.44 ± 2.987◆
NGT	149	95	63.8	54	36.2	2.81±3.536
Total	434	297	68.4	141	32.5	3.02±4.114

* The caries rate of the three groups $X^2 = 2.351 p = 0.309 > 0.05$ The caries of the three groups were tested by LSD:

△Compared with the IGR group $p = 0.005 < 0.05$, ▲Compared with the control group $p = 0.040 < 0.05$

◆Compared with the control group $p = 0.443 > 0.05$

The proportion of caries and missing fillings in the three groups was 25.6%, 26.4% and 48.0% in DM, 28.1%, 10.5% and 61.4% in IGR group, and 34.1%, 28.2% and 37.7% in control group. The proportion of caries and missing fillings in the three groups was statistically significant ($P < 0.01$). After chi-square segmentation, the difference between DM group

and IGR group, and between DM group and control group was statistically significant ($P < 0.01$), as shown in Table 3. The number of teeth with caries that could not be filled or decayed to residual roots that could not be filled was up to 10 teeth per diabetic patient, up to 7 teeth per person in IGR group, and up to 14 teeth per person in control group. The DM group had the largest number of teeth lost due to caries, which was 145.

Table 3 – Comparison of caries, loss of teeth and fillings in DM group, IGR group and control group.

Group	Dental caries	Caries(%)	Missing of teeth	Loss of teeth(%)	Tooth filling	repair(%)	Total caries
DM	141	25.6	145	26.4	264	48.0	550△▲
IGR	96	28.1	36	10.5	210	61.4	342◆
NGT	143	34.1	118	28.2	158	37.7	419
Total	380	29.0	299	22.8	632	48.2	1311*

* Comparison of caries and missing fillings composition ratio among the three groups $X^2 = 58.925$, $P = 0.000$ After split chi-square test △ Compared with IGR group $X^2 = 33.665$ $P = 0.000$

▲ Compared with control group $X^2 = 11.919$ $P = 0.003$ ◆ Compared with control group $X^2 = 53.00$ $P = 0.000$

Comparison of Saliva volume of DM group, IGR group and control group (mL/10min), salivary pH and fasting blood sugar (mmol/L) show that: saliva of DM group and IGR group the amount (mL/10min) and saliva pH value were significantly lower than those of the healthy control group population ($P < 0.01$), while the fasting blood sugar value (mmol/L) was significantly higher for the healthy control group ($P < 0.01$), see Table 4

Table 4 – Comparison of saliva volume (mL/10min), saliva pH and fasting blood sugar among the three groups.

Group	Number of cases	Saliva volume(Mean)	Saliva volume(SD)	Saliva pH(Mean)	Saliva pH(SD)	Fasting blood sugar(Mean)	Fasting blood sugar(SD)
DM	145	1.304△	1.199	7.101△	0.556	7.683△★	2.746
IGR	140	1.396▲	1.171	7.047△	0.479	5.671▲	0.729
NGT	149	1.928	1.656	7.379	0.485	4.998	0.440
Total	434	1.548	1.390	7.183	0.527	6.128	2.045

△Compared with the control group, $P = 0.000 < 0.01$ ★Compared with the IGR group, $P = 0.000 < 0.01$ ▲Compared with the control group, $P = 0.001 < 0.01$

The results of this study showed that the number of teeth with caries that could not be filled or caries that were in a residual root state and could not be filled was up to 10 teeth per diabetic patient, up to 7 teeth per IGR group, and up to 14 teeth per control group. This situation may be caused by the following reasons: first, patients do not pay enough attention to their oral health and do not seek medical treatment in time; second, oral medical resources are limited and it is inconvenient for patients to seek medical treatment. Therefore, oral medical workers should strengthen oral health education for this group, improve self-oral health awareness, develop good oral hygiene habits, brush teeth in the morning and evening, rinse mouth after meals, and perform oral care regularly, in order to reverse this situation. At the same time, relevant parties need to pay more attention to the development of oral medical care and provide a variety of oral medical services.

Discussion

Diabetes is a metabolic syndrome characterized by persistent high blood sugar, which causes metabolic disorders of sugar, protein, fat and subsequently water and electrolytes, resulting in damage to various organs and decreased function. The increased blood sugar concentration in diabetic patients affects normal blood flow, enhances platelet adhesion and aggregation, reduces anticoagulant factors, increases red blood cell fragility, causes tissue hypoxia and vascular endothelial damage, and facilitates the invasion and infection of bacteria and their toxins, leading to aggravated tissue damage[9]. Diabetic patients often have reduced saliva volume, decreased salivary flow rate, reduced buffering capacity, and changes in composition[10]. In particular, the glucose concentration in saliva increases[11] and

the pH value of saliva decreases, which increases the number of cariogenic *Streptococcus mutans* in saliva compared with normal people, thereby increasing the risk of caries in diabetic patients. The results of this study showed that the dental caries rate of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus was not significantly different from that of patients with impaired glucose regulation and healthy subjects, but the dental caries rate was significantly different from the latter two groups, indicating that the dental caries of patients with diabetes mellitus was more serious. Some studies have found that there is a correlation between salivary secretion dysfunction and diabetes mellitus. Patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus have more obvious symptoms of dry mouth or hyposaliva secretion. When the saliva flow rate of diabetic patients at rest is less than 0.01 mL/min, it often leads to an increase in the dental caries rate [12]. The results of this study showed that the saliva volume (mL/10min) and saliva pH value of the diabetes group and the impaired glucose regulation group were significantly lower than those of the healthy subjects, while the fasting blood glucose value was significantly higher than that of the healthy subjects. Saliva is a mixture of secretions of the large and small salivary glands in the mouth and gingival sulcus fluid. It is the external environment of the teeth. Its quantity and quality changes are closely related to the occurrence and development of dental caries. In addition to rinsing the tooth surface, the lysozyme and ammonium salts in saliva have the effect of inhibiting bacteria. Elements such as calcium, phosphorus, and fluorine can exchange ions with tooth enamel, causing tooth remineralization, thus reducing the caries rate. The salivary flow rate of diabetic patients decreases, which reduces the flushing effect on the tooth surface and the buffering capacity of the large amount of organic acids produced by the metabolism of sugar by bacteria in dental plaque, reducing the self-cleaning ability of the oral cavity, leading to an increased risk of caries in diabetic patients. The results of the second national oral health epidemiological sampling survey showed that the caries rate of the elderly aged 65-74 in my country was as high as 64.75% [13]. The average age of the population in this study was 65 years old. The results of this study showed that the caries rates of the DM group and the control group (66.9% and 63.8%, respectively) were comparable to those of the elderly, and were lower than the results of the third national oral health epidemiological sampling survey (98.6%) [14]. The caries rate of the IGR population (72.1%) was higher than that of the second national oral health epidemiological sampling survey. The results of this study are different from the report of Xie Sijing et al. in China [15]. IGR population was once called prediabetes population, which is a high-risk population for diabetes [10], an important stage leading to the occurrence and death of diabetes and cardiovascular events, and an important risk factor for the occurrence of coronary heart disease [16]. About 50% of people with impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) (Note: IGT is an impaired state of IGR, see grouping) will develop type 2 diabetes within 10 years, and the number of people who die from cardiovascular disease within 9 years is 34% higher than that of the normal population [17]. At present, foreign scholars have reported many studies on the correlation between diabetes and dental caries, but the research results are controversial [18]. Domestic research reports are relatively few, but they are also controversial. The reasons for the different research results may be related to the different research subjects, the technical level of the examiners and the differences in research standards. The subjects of this study are faculty members of a certain university community. Most of them are highly educated and may have a stronger awareness of oral health care, better economic income, and better oral health care than the general population. In addition, due to the advancement of tooth filling and repair technology, the filled teeth can be so real that they may be missed. The elderly have memory loss and it is difficult to tell which teeth have been filled. This is also one of the reasons for the deviation of research results. To obtain convincing research results, a relatively large sample and strict quality control are still needed. However, the results of this study showed that the caries rate and caries of IGR population were not statistically significant compared with the control group, which indicates that abnormal blood sugar may damage the hard tissue of the tooth later than other organs.

Conclusion

Diabetic Patients have more severe dental caries than those with impaired glucose regulation and healthy people. Controlling diabetes may help reduce the number of dental caries.

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